

Workshop for the 2020 European Microwave Week

For any questions please contact Dr. Laura Anitori (workshops@eumw2020.org).

Organizer(s)

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Half-day
workshop

Conference¹:
EuMC
EuMIC
EuRAD

Workshop Title:

From enabling GaN Technology to high-performing Space-borne SSPAs at millimeter-wave

Topic: **GaN SSPA for space applications**

Workshop Abstract

The development for next generation Very High Throughput Satellites (vHTS) systems, will make use of Ka/Q/V gateways, where the forward payload link will operate in K-band. This kind of spacecraft will offer high capacity, large number of users and communication volumes (1 Terabit/s per satellite), with lower cost per GBPS, increasing the flexibility being the satellite capacity allocated only when-&-where it is needed. Traditionally, demand for high power levels at high frequencies has been satisfied by using TWTAs as amplifying device; this is because SSPA technology was unable to attain similar performance levels. However, technological advancements such as linearization, miniaturisation, and the use of different materials such as GaN, have levelled the playing field open the actual possibility to replace TWTA with SSPAs.

This workshop aims to report about recent progress on millimetre wave GaN-based SSPAs for space applications, starting from the assessment of the scenarios, in both ground and space segments, to the actual SSPA design, realization and tests, also describing state-of-art GaN semiconductor technologies.

Speakers

1. Speaker's Name: Fabio Vitobello

Affiliation: REA

Presentation Title: Space Initiatives at European Level

Speaker's Email: Fabio.VITOBELLO@ec.europa.eu

2. Speaker's Name: Dr. Václav Valenta

Affiliation: European Space Agency

Presentation Title: SSPAs for high-throughput satellites: challenges and solutions

Speaker's Email: Vaclav.Valenta@esa.int

3. Speaker's Name: BOUSCASSE, François

Affiliation: Airbus Defence

Presentation Title: The space market needs in term of SSPAs and HPAs for 5G application

Speaker's Email: francois.bouscasse@airbus.com

Summary (2-3 sentences):

The apparition of mobile connectivity has impacted the consumers' habits over these last years, and as a consequence the data volume requirement is reaching a level unseen before. The capacity demand is expected to be increased by a factor 1000, while the traffic will be mainly dedicated to video (2/3rd). To cope with this challenge, the 5G will be the global network backbone with major role for Telecommunications Satellites. The data consumption increase and terrestrial competition lead to a reduction of the capacity buying price (in \$/Gbps or \$/transponder). Needs in term of high power amplifier will follow the trend, increase of power and bandwidth at lower cost.

4. Speaker's Name: Ernesto Limiti

Affiliation: University of Roma Tor Vergata

Presentation Title: MiGaNSOS: Millimetre wave Gallium Nitride Space evaluation and application to Observation Satellites

Speaker's Email: limiti@ing.uniroma2.it

5. Speaker's Name: Rocco Giofrè, Paolo Colantonio

Affiliation: University of Roma Tor Vergata

Presentation Title: Design of high efficiency power amplifier based on GaN technology for Ka-Band

Speaker's Email: giofr@ing.uniroma2.it; paolo.colantonio@uniroma2.it

Summary (2-3 sentences):

The design and experimental characterization of MMICs PA, specifically conceived for next generation Ka-band Very High Throughput Satellites (vHTS) are presented. The developed MMICs have been adopted as building block for a space-borne SSPA targeting more than 120W of output power in the overall Ka downlink band (17.3-20.2 GHz). The MMICs have been implemented on the commercial 100 nm gate length GaN-Si process from OMMIC. The designs steps will be deeply discussed focusing on the peculiarities and challenges of the space applications. Experimental results on the realized MMICs will be presented together with a preliminary system level evaluation of the overall SSPA.

6. Speaker's Name: Chiara Ramella, Corrado Florian

Affiliation: Politecnico di Turin, University of Bologna

Presentation Title: Ka-Band HPA MMICs for Cryosat-2 Follow-On mission (CS2-FO)

Speaker's Email: chiara.ramella@polito.it; corrado.florian@unibo.it